

A Study on Cosmetics Consumption among School Boys in Periyakulam Taluk of Theni District

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Abstract

Cosmetics products consumption plays a vital role in marketing. The study influenced by various factors of cosmetics products. In this study titled "A Study on cosmetics consumption among teenage boys in periyakulam taluk of Theni district." A sample of 150 boys students have been selected by the random sampling method. The statistical tools used for analysis like percentage. An important indicator of marketing is the success of an enterprise in the hands of the number of its loyal customers. Here the researcher has taken the teenage school students as sample respondents. In this study concentrate, the school students were loyal customers of cosmetics. The study concludes the cosmetics consumption of younger generation.

Introduction

Cosmetics market in India attitude a long glowing heritage of cosmetic and beauty, aesthetic makeup products are being used since olden days, and nowadays it appears like a booming economy in India which would be the largest cosmetic consuming country in a next few decades. While the demand for beautifying substances are growing day by day, a large number of local as well as international manufacturers gradually extend their ranges and products in different provinces of India. Indian cosmetic Industry had rapid growth in the last couple of years, growing at a CAGR of around 7.5% between 2006 and 2008. While this is due to the improving purchasing power and increasing fashion consciousness, the industry is expected to maintain the growth momentum during the period 2009-2012.

In the Indian Cosmetic Industry, both electronic, as well as print media are playing a vital role in spreading awareness about cosmetic products and developing fashion consciousness among the Indian consumers. Due to the development of satellite television channels as well as the Internet in the modern day, the Indian consumers are constantly being updated the new cosmetic products, translating into the desire to purchase them.

Review of Literature

Dr. S. Mahalingam, P. Nandhakumar (2012) "A Study on consumer behaviour towards selected FMCGs in Coimbatore City" focuses their

efforts on analysis the socio-economic profile of the sample respondents and their shopping pattern and assesses the factors influencing the customers to purchase the selected FMCG products.

Devibala, P & Rangaswamy, A (2011) in his article “Consumer Preference for cosmetics among college girls in Tirunelveli and Thoothukudi”. The researcher focuses the costumer preferences for cosmetics among college girls and whether the college girls satisfied with the brand available, analysis and understand whether they are satisfied with the present price of cosmetics

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the frequency of using cosmetics of sample respondents.
2. To study the type of product preferred by sample respondents.
3. To analyse the preferred factors while purchasing cosmetics by sample respondents.
4. To analyze the source of information for sample respondents.
5. To offer suggestions for cosmetics consumption.

Area of the Study

This paper has attempted to analysis the consumption of cosmetics among teenage boys in Periyakulam taluk of Theni District. This study conducted among Three schools from Devathanapatti, Genguvarpatti and Silvarpatti Higher Secondary School students in Periyakulam Taluk.

Scope of the Study

This study confined to cosmetics consumption among the boys students in selected three schools from the periyakulam taluk only.

Period of the Study

The study has been undertaken during a period of three months from November 2018 to February 2019.

Sources of Data

The Study has been collected from primary and secondary sources of data. Both Primary and Secondary research were used for the purpose of answering research questions. The Primary data were collected from sample respondents with the help of interview schedule. Secondary data was derived from bibliographic, internet sources, books, magazines and journals, students, parents, teachers, beauty parlours, cosmetics shop keeper and sales force.

Sampling Design

This research is descriptive in nature. Sample design is resolute before data is collected. Random sampling method is used to collect the data from the population. Simple random sampling method is used to collect data. Data are collected directly from the population and from students. A sample of 150 school students from selected. 50 students from each selected schools has been taken for this study.

Tools for Analysis

The statistical tool used for the analysis of this study is simple percentage technique. After the collection of data from the questionnaire, editing was made watchfully. Based on the responses of the samples, tables were prepared. The data collected were analyzed and interpreted with the help of tables & figures.

Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1
Frequency of using Cosmetics

Sr.No.	Frequency of using Cosmetics	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Daily	60	40
2	Weekly	30	20
3	Monthly	40	27
4	Festivals	20	13
	Total	150	100

Table 1 shows that out of 150 respondents 40 % are using cosmetics daily, 20% are using weekly, 20% are using monthly and 13% are using festival times only.

Table 2
Type of product preferred by respondents

Sr. No.	Type of product preferred by respondents	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Ayurvedic	60	40
2	Chemical	20	13
3	Both	70	47
	Total	150	100

Above table indicates 40% of the respondents preferred ayurvedic products, 13% of the respondents preferred chemical based products and 47% of the respondents preferred both type of products. It means that today's consumers are changing their attitude towards more healthier & natural cosmetic products as a whole.

Table 3
Preferred Factors While Purchasing Cosmetics

Sr. No	Preferred Factors While Purchasing Cosmetics	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Brand Name	50	33
2	Quality	60	40
3	Price	30	20
4	Others	10	07
		150	100

Above table shows that 40% of the respondents give preference to quality of product, 33% of the respondents consider brand name, 20% of the respondents consider price of the product & 7% of the respondents consider other factors.

Table 4
Source of Information for respondents

Sr. No.	Source of Information for respondents	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Magazines/Newspapers	32	21
2	Beautician	10	07
3	Friends	10	07
4	Relatives	20	13
5	Doctors	3	2
6	Commercial Media	70	47
7	Other	5	3
	Total	150	100

The above table indicates that 47% of the respondents collected information from commercial media & internet, 07% of respondents from friends, 21% of respondents from magazines & newspapers, 20% of respondents from beauticians & relatives.

Findings

1. Majority of the student's were choose to purchase cosmetic products from stable stores, private bazaars & medical shops as they feel it is easily available and products are in good quality.
2. Quality was plays a important role for purchase of cosmetics by the students when compared to the price.
3. Television is the commonly used device that impact on consumer, used for receiving information about the product.
4. The students who are using internet is more educated about the product details..

Suggestions

1. The Respondents feel that the prices of cosmetics are comparatively higher. Hence it is suggested that manufacturer should concentrate on product changes and diversification in the cosmetics through which they can reduce the prices.
2. A proper communication should be created with doctors, beauticians and should be involved in advertisement to make them more attractive, affective and reliable.
3. Marketer should include your attitude and personal appeal in their advertising communication as the consumer buy cosmetic products on their own.

Conclusion

It is concluded from this study that cosmetic sector is growing and will continue to grow very fast. In India the market share of cosmetic industry contributes a considerable amount of FMCG sector, which is continuously increasing from year to year. Quality is the main motivating factor for the consumer by the product of cosmetic. From this analysis, it is inferred that the respondents given greater important to the factors of quality and the health care with compared to factors in the selection of cosmetic products.

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